

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПУТЕЙ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ПРОЦЕССА ТРУДОУСТРОЙСТВА ВЫПУСКНИКОВ ВУЗА И ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ОРИЕНТАЦИИ УЧАЩИХСЯ

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IMPROVING THE WAYS OF MANAGING THE PROCESS OF EMPLOYMENT OF UNIVERSITY GRADUATES AND PROFESSIONAL ORIENTATION OF STUDENTS

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Аннотация

В статье рассмотрено сетевое взаимодействие и использование дистанционных технологий в образовательных учреждениях разных стран.

Abstract

The article considers network interaction and the use of distance technologies in educational institutions of different countries.

Ключевые слова: информационная система, трудоустройство, дистанционные технологии, непрерывное образование, сетевое взаимодействие.

Keywords: information system, employment, distance technologies, continuing education, networking.

Статья подготовлена в рамках проекта гранта на коммерциализацию результатов научной и научно-технической деятельности молодых ученых «Jas ǵalym» Жетысуский университет имени И.Жансугурова.

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Education today is not just an opportunity to gain professional and relevant knowledge, but also a complex focused on new economic conditions, a variety of skills and abilities, flexibility and continuity of professional training. At the same time, there is a clear imbalance in the labor market between the professional aspirations of applicants and the requirements of employers. One of the reasons for the current situation is the lack of an affordable, high-quality and effective tool that contributes to the successful implementation of professional qualities at the place of employment after receiving professional education and satisfaction with the position. The main conditions for the realization of successful professional self-determination are: understanding of the personal and social significance of the

right choice of profession, the presence of a professional ideal, the formation of professionally important qualities and motives for choosing a profession, compliance of personal qualities and labor market requirements to the qualifications of applicants. Currently, information about the professions in demand, the nature of professional work, the level of wages and professional educational institutions where you can master the profession is available on various Internet sites. The Internet offers a lot of tests that you can take online and get recommendations on choosing a profession based on the results of testing. However, the analysis and interpretation of the results in order to further choose the path of self-realization (training or employment) is carried out independently. As a rule, in relation to the labor market of a particular city or the specialties of a particular educational institution, this is quite difficult to implement.

In the modern world, the central process of formation and change of society and its environment is global informatization. This is due to the increasing role of information, and the increase in its role in all spheres of human life. Therefore, the introduction and improvement of information systems in education is a necessary step in the development of modern society.

Currently, the competence of a specialist is formed not only by the total amount of knowledge in the field of professional activity, but also by the ability to use the Internet, as well as programs necessary for the successful implementation of practical activities, and one of the important skills remains to be able to navigate the updated information space.

The education system in the new realities requires innovative approaches, as well as a multivariate learning environment is being formed for the realization of students' personal potential, as well as the development of their creative and non-stereotypical thinking, which is characterized by the ability to quickly, flexibly and with originality put forward new ideas. Schoolchildren raised in the new environment of education tomorrow become teachers, doctors, pilots, specialists in their field. But how does the transition between the student and specialist stages take place? This transition marks a stage in the formation of personal values, its orientation and life path, which is an important step in the life of every person.

Therefore, there is a need to change career guidance activities and the introduction of information systems to improve the established traditional methods of choosing a profession using information technologies that facilitate certain stages in the formation of professional formation and growth of future specialists.

The analysis of the scientific literature on the problem under study and practical experience shows that many economic, theoretical and practical problems of employment and its close connection with the quality of the educational process have not been sufficiently investigated, a systematic analysis of the content and technologies of employment support for graduates has not been carried out, effective methods of organizing and managing employment processes have not been developed.

Currently, there are no existing and operating systems for this problem, the issue is poorly understood and needs to be resolved. The proposed information system solves important social problems of graduates such as corruption, reducing the unemployment rate and increasing the competitiveness of future specialists. Automated actions implemented on the website and the availability of materials prevent any external interference by ensuring privacy and solving the problems described above.

The introduction of an information system for the professional orientation of graduates in educational institutions will significantly increase the level of employment of specialists.

The results obtained during the implementation of this project will become real prerequisites for saturating the educational environment of educational institutions of the Republic of Kazakhstan with scientifically based developments and new innovative technologies in the system of continuing education.

As the main mechanism of information exchange, network interaction and remote technologies make it possible to realize synergetic effects in collective scientific and educational activities, make it possible to use the advantages of the network and remote technol-

ogies in improving the efficiency of educational institutions, optimizing costs, improving the quality of educational programs and academic mobility.

Since practically in terms of terminology, the concept of a network and a cluster are combined, and their differences are leveled, the conditions highlighted by M. Voynarenko can be used as prerequisites for successful network interaction. The described interaction has been developing more and more actively in recent years in order to ensure continuing education. Continuing education within the framework of the network interaction of educational institutions involves specialized training. Current graduates are well aware that obtaining a university diploma is not a guarantee of cloudless existence until old age.

According to statistics of the Republic of Kazakhstan, in some regions of the country up to 50% of university graduates and up to 64% of graduates of secondary specialized educational institutions change their profession immediately after graduation. A huge number of young people are forced to re-solve the problem of organizing their professional career. There is a clear problem here: while a student is finishing his studies, he finds himself unclaimed in the rapidly changing world of information technology.

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, according to the data of the State Pension Payment Center, the employment rate of all university graduates in 2017 decreased by 10% compared to 2016. In 2015, 29,618 people out of 35,790 graduates who studied under the state order were employed, in 2016 out of 41,680 people - 35,332 and in 2017 out of 37,549 people - 27,006 graduates. Although Kazakhstan's education system is known for its breadth and versatility of knowledge, however, this knowledge is difficult to transfer to practice. As a result, graduates of universities and secondary vocational institutions face problems in finding employment, which, in turn, exacerbates the problems of unemployment and social stability.

The European model of education follows a different path, teaching students applied disciplines. The study of foreign practice shows that training in the structures of additional vocational education can be carried out in different ways: as training in various courses without issuing diplomas (informal training); as training in various educational programs leading to obtaining a new specialty or professional qualification; and as independent studies with the right to take an exam and receive a diploma, certificate or license. In many educational institutions in all English-speaking countries, students can study both compulsory subjects and subjects in the direction of specialization and additional subjects of choice, so the American specificity is that such a division is already assumed by the educational system itself and is reflected in the diploma received.

Germany in accordance with the concept of continuing education in this country, the basic center for obtaining such education is specially created educational and simulation firms, most of which are organized by the state and private business jointly. In accordance with this, if such centers are organized on the

basis of state universities with the participation of leading companies-market leaders, then students will not only be able to plunge into the practical aspects of the courses they study, but also get real skills and abilities that will help them find employment in the future.

In the USA, the system of professional development and, as a result, wage growth requires regular certifications, then constant self-education encourages employees to self-improvement. Also, as you know, the spirit of competition and serious competition among qualified personnel is very strong in the USA, therefore, in order to keep their place, employees must provide a self-education report, as well as make reports or reports after completing courses, as well as participate in projects regulated on the basis of new knowledge. Such a system could not only increase the efficiency of domestic employees of firms, but also bring considerable profit to organizations that employ highly qualified personnel.

In Russia, there are quite interesting practices of networking, designed to varying degrees, at different levels of education. So, in the system of higher education, bright examples of universities working on the network principle and broadcasting their experience are: Kazan National Research Technological University and the National Research Nuclear University "MEPhI", which has 32 basic departments from 43 enterprises, organized a network school. In the school education system, MBOU Kantemirovsky Lyceum carries out network interaction with schools of the Voronezh region.

In Kazakhstan, the issues of organizing a network form of educational programs at the university level are being considered. The experience of Tomsk State University and S.Toraighyrov Pavlodar State University in the development and implementation of a joint two-degree master's program is interesting. In the field of secondary education, the issue of creating a pedagogical network community and its impact on the professional growth of a teacher is discussed.

However, modern Kazakh education has two extremes – traditional attitudes towards high academic (fundamental) and a new attitude towards a competence-based approach. It is necessary to find a balance between them in the actual practice of continuing education.

An important aspect of the implementation of the system of basic, general and additional education should be considered the trend towards the active introduction of modern educational technologies in regions remote from educational centers.

The rapid development of information and communication technologies, the emergence of new opportunities for their use in educational practice encourage us to look for the potential for the spread of network

interaction and distance technologies of basic, general and additional education in the organizational component of the activities of educational institutions.

The introduction of networking and distance technologies in educational institutions will allow us to fully address the issues of improving the quality of education through the expansion of subject areas, the introduction of integrated educational programs, the development of special projects for working with schoolchildren, teachers, parents, as well as the full inclusion of people with disabilities in society.

References

1. Войнаренко М.П. Кластерные технологии в системе развития предпринимательства, интеграции и привлечения инвестиций / М.П. Войнаренко // Социальные аспекты и финансирование промышленной реструктуризации: региональный форум. – М., 2003.
2. Гарифуллина Н.Ю. О результатах мониторинга трудоустройства выпускников в 83 субъектах Российской Федерации // Трудоустройство выпускников учреждений профессионального образования: мониторинг, анализ и опыт лучшей практики. 2013.
3. Новикова Д.М. Инновационные подходы к обновлению системы высшего образования и повышению качества подготовки специалистов//Актуальные проблемы социально-экономического развития России. – 2014, № 1, С. 22-24
4. Аналитический отчет по реализации принципов Болонского процесса в Республике Казахстан, 2018 год. – Астана: Центр Болонского процесса и академической мобильности МОН РК, 2018. - 64 с.
5. Shannon, D. (2009) 'Continuing Higher Education in America: A Profile', International Journal of Continuing Education and Lifelong Learning, 1(2), 19-39.
6. Marcella Milana, Lesley McBain - Adult and Continuing Education Policy in the USA/ Global Perspectives on Adult Education and Learning Policy, pp.44-59/ DOI: 10.1057/9781137388254_4 / January 2015. From: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/304819001_Adult_and_Continuing_Education_Policy_in_the_USA
7. Демкин В.П., Джарасова Г.С., Испулов Н.А., Омирбаев С.М., Отт М.А., Пфейфер Н.Э., Руденко Т.В. Сетевое взаимодействие вузов как фактор повышения качества образовательных программ. Открытое дистанционное образование. 2014. №4(56) - С. 40-44